

ISic0960

I.Sicily inscription 0960

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 90

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐκομήθη Μαρ
2. κελλα τῆς πέν τε τοῦ μενός
4. Ἰουνίου μν
5. ησθῆ Κύριος
6. τῆς κοιμήσε
7. ὡς σου

Apparatus

Text of Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492599

EDCS 39102126

PHI 140450

Bibliography

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